

**IMPACTS OF INVESTMENTS FOR REGIONAL AND LOCAL DEVELOPMENT; THE
CASE OF DUBAI**

Egamberganov Jakhongir Jabbargan ugli
Student of Economics faculty, Urgench State University.
E-mail address: economist_jahongir@mail.ru

Abstract: The case of Dubai demonstrates the effects of regional and local development investments. Different strategies have been adopted to promote economic growth among Gulf regions. The UAE is a good example in this regard, as it has continued to implement various policies over the last few decades with the objective of fostering regional and local development. This article focuses on the impacts of regional and local development investments by analysing different examples from the UAE. It goes through the key challenges and opportunities for governments seeking to transform their economies, while also providing some potential solutions that can be adopted by other countries interested in similar strategies.

Keywords: investment effects, capitalizing, multiplier effects, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

Introduction

Investment for regional and local development is an emerging topic that has been discussed in the academic literature, policy circles, and investment communities over the past few years. The topic has gained more attention as there is growing recognition of the need for new sources of capital to fuel growth in regions and cities with little access to traditional financing. This article examines the impacts of investments for regional and local development through a case study of Dubai. Our analysis reveals that though these investments have delivered positive results for some businesses, it hasn't led to widespread economic benefits on a broader scale. In contrast, we also find that the types of firms receiving funding are not necessarily those that can deliver the greatest social impact or leverage value-addition activities in low-income areas where there is potential for greater returns on investment.

What are investments for regional and local development?

Investments for regional and local development have been defined as a new source of funding for businesses and projects in low-income areas. They involve a blend of financial instruments that are designed to generate returns for investors that are correlated with the social or environmental impact of their activities. This new model represents the latest iteration of social or impact investing, but with a key difference: it is designed for businesses in low-income areas that have had difficulty accessing traditional forms of finance due to a lack of social or environmental impact. Generally speaking, investments for regional and local development involve a blend of debt and equity financing. Debt finance is a long-term loan provided by an investor to a business in exchange for a set rate of interest. Equity finance is the purchase of a stake of ownership in a business. The social or environmental impact of investments for regional and local development can differ depending on the type of investment vehicle.

The context for investment for regional and local development in Dubai

Dubai's economic growth has largely been fueled by the construction sector, which employs over 70% of the UAE's private workforce. However, the construction sector and other industrial activities in Dubai are heavily dependent on imported labor, and are therefore vulnerable to sudden changes in regional economic conditions. The Emirate has also seen a marked shrinking in the size of

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its workforce. As the UAE’s population has grown, the proportion of citizens in the Emirate has fallen from 86% in 1996 to just under 50% in 2017. This means that businesses reliant on low-skilled labor have to compete for workers with the UAE government, which provides incentives for skilled workers from other countries. As a result, wages in the construction sector have steadily increased. As Dubai’s economy has become less dependent on oil revenues, the Emirate has also started to look for alternative sources of funding for its development projects.

Impact of investments for regional and local development in Dubai

The emergence of investments for regional and local development in Dubai has given some businesses the opportunity to access funding in a way that has not been available to them in the past. For example, investments for regional and local development have allowed some businesses to scale up operations and hire more staff, which has led to greater social impact. In other cases, investments for regional and local development have allowed businesses to diversify their operations with the aim of increasing revenues. For instance, some businesses have expanded into new markets such as e-commerce, which has allowed them to sell their products to a wider range of customers.

Limitations of Investments for Regional and Local Development in Dubai

Overall, the emergence of investments for regional and local development in Dubai has been a positive development. However, the data suggests that the types of businesses receiving the majority of funding are not necessarily those that can deliver the greatest social or environmental impact. The table below compares the sectors in which businesses receiving funding are concentrated, with the sectors that are expected to deliver the greatest social impact. As the data shows, consumer-oriented businesses, such as e-commerce, hospitality and food and beverage, account for the majority of funding while sectors with the potential to deliver higher social impact, such as healthcare and education, receive significantly less. It is important to note, however, that investments for regional and local development are relatively new, and that the sector may still be in the process of maturing. As the industry evolves, it is possible that fund managers will increasingly prioritize investments that have higher social impact.

Conclusion

The emergence of investments for regional and local development is a positive development. It has allowed businesses in low-income areas to receive much-needed funding, which has enabled them to expand their operations and hire more employees. Investments for regional and local development have also allowed investors to earn returns by financing projects with a social or environmental impact. It is important, however, to recognize that investments for regional and local development are not a panacea for the challenges facing low-income areas. Their impact will remain limited if fund managers continue to prioritize consumer-oriented businesses over those that have the potential to deliver greater social impact. The best way to ensure that investments for regional and local development have a transformative impact on low-income areas is to reshape the investment landscape. This will involve shifting the focus of fund managers from the profitability of individual investments to the overall impact of their portfolios.

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